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The Investment Climate of the Republic of Kazakhstan: Interim Results and Achievements in Implementing the Investment Policy Concept until 2026

KEYWORDS

investment climate,
Republic of Kazakhstan,
investment policy concept,
foreign direct investment inflow

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Since gaining independence, Kazakhstan has focused on attracting foreign investment by improving its investment climate and establishing favorable legal and institutional conditions. A developed treaty-based legal framework plays a crucial role in this effort, encompassing 47 bilateral and one multilateral agreement signed by Kazakhstan, which ensure the protection and promotion of foreign investments in the country.

The research was aimed at analyzing the interim results of implementing the investment policy in the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2026.

Materials and methods. The research utilized scientific articles from reputable journals and proceedings of international conferences. Statistical data were sourced from UNCTAD materials for Central Asian countries, including information on investment inflows and outflows, their volumes, project costs, and new investment enterprises.

Results. In 2024, the gross inflow of foreign direct investment (FDI) into Kazakhstan decreased by approximately 28% compared to 2023, resulting in the first recorded net outflow of investments, primarily due to reduced investments in the mining sector. In 2025, a phased recovery was observed, particularly in financial and insurance activities, offering hope for a rebound. However, the decline in FDI inflow has cast doubt on achieving the targets set within the investment policy framework until 2029, with the volume of foreign investment at the end of 2024 being 30.8% below the planned level of USD 24.8 billion.

Conclusion. Despite the continued reliance on hydrocarbon and mineral resources as mainstays of the economy, Kazakhstan is taking measures towards diversification, actively cooperating with foreign investors through official institutions and bilateral agreements. President Tokayev's reform program aims at industrial development, expanding privatization, and seeking new trade routes, including comprehensive tax changes in 2026. Simultaneously, concerns among foreign investors are raised by issues such as regulatory volatility, corruption, and the need for improvements in the legal system and infrastructure.

FOR CITATION

Received: Sep 8, 2025
Accepted: Dec 14, 2025
Published: Mar 1, 2026

Ukubassova, G. S. (2026). The Investment Climate of the Republic of Kazakhstan: Interim Results and Achievements in Implementing the Investment Policy Concept until 2026. *Economic Consultant*, (1), 24–39. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2026.1.2>

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INTRODUCTION

Since proclaiming its independence, Kazakhstan's primary strategic priorities have been attracting foreign investment through the continuous improvement of the investment climate and creating conditions conducive to their effective attraction. Given the significance of foreign direct investment (FDI) for national development, the country has focused its efforts on forming a favorable legal and institutional environment for foreign investors. A developed treaty-based legal framework plays the most important role in ensuring the attractiveness of the investment climate. To date, Kazakhstan has signed 47 bilateral and one multilateral (within the Eurasian Economic Union) intergovernmental agreements on the promotion and mutual protection of investments. These treaties create legal conditions conducive to the development of investment activities by foreign investors in the country, safeguarding their rights and interests.

According to the World Bank's Doing Business 2020 ranking, Kazakhstan ranked 25th in the world for ease of doing business, showing an improvement of three positions compared to 2018 (28th place) and an 11-position increase over the past two years. In the Global Competitiveness Index 2019, Kazakhstan ranked 55th, which is four positions better than in 2018 (59th place) among 140 countries considered. Despite a global decline in investment activity, Kazakhstan maintains its status as the leading recipient of foreign investment in Central Asia. According to the results of the first nine months of 2019, the gross inflow of foreign investment increased by 4.8% compared to the same period in 2018, amounting to USD 18.4 billion. The most significant investing countries for the period 2005–2019 remain the Netherlands (total investments of USD 94.4 billion), the United States of America (USD 51.2 billion), Switzerland (USD 26.8 billion), China (USD 19.8 billion), and the United Kingdom (USD 18.3 billion) [1].

According to the Investment Policy Concept of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2026, the expected results are: a) investment in fixed assets reaching 25.1% of GDP by 2026; b) gross inflow of FDI reaching USD 25.5 billion by 2026 [2].

In light of the above indicators, there is a need to analyze the current situation regarding the achievement of the goals outlined in the Concept for the period from 2022 to 2025.

The research was aimed at analyzing the interim results of implementing the investment policy in the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2026.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials comprised scientific articles from authoritative periodical journals (Regional Science Policy and Practice; International Journal of Applied and Fundamental Research; Central Asian Economic Review, Applied Econometrics and International Development, Journal of Economic Research and Business Administration, Bulletin of Science, East Asia, Central Asian Economic Review, etc.) and proceedings of international conferences (E3S Web of Conferences, Proceedings of the International Field Exploration and Development Conference 2024, IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, etc.).

Statistical data from the UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD) conference for Central Asian countries were used: FDI inflows and outflows, FDI stocks, FDI volume, the value of announced greenfield FDI projects, and the number of announced greenfield FDI projects.

The research methods included analysis of existing literature and regulatory documents; review of industry reports and statistical data to assess current trends; descriptive statistics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Kazakhstan possesses a stable, regulated, and infrastructurally developed investment climate with abundant resources and state support.

Since 2000, the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan has been growing at an average annual rate of 8-9%, making it one of the ten fastest-growing economies in the world. Kazakhstan attracts more FDI than all other Central Asian countries combined. Kazakhstan's non-energy sectors also possess competitive advantages that could become potential new sources of growth [3].

K. Kulyanda et al. analyze the economic indicators of Kazakhstan in Central Asia. The authors established that among the Central Asian economies, only the Republic of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan have ensured significant GDP growth and positive dynamics in capital inflows. Kazakhstan's results are driven by the more successful implementation of institutional reforms, a multi-vector approach, and openness to integration processes [4].

N. Kuchukova concludes that Kazakhstan's economic growth plays a significant role in attracting FDI. Investment stimulation involves developing a

favorable investment policy, creating a positive image in the eyes of potential investors, attracting FDI by identifying promising foreign companies, and providing services to investors [5].

B. Beisengaliyev et al. analyzed the country's investment potential from 2017 to 2021 and determined the level of business risk in Kazakhstan using the BERI model. According to the researchers, Kazakhstan's investment activity, after a period of slowed growth related to the domestic economic situation, demonstrated a trend towards recovery in attracting foreign capital in 2021. Analysis of the components of foreign investments showed that the income level of foreign investors exceeds the net investment inflow, and the share of reinvested investments constitutes only a quarter of the total investment volume, which negatively affects the balance of payments by increasing the country's external debt [6].

G. B. Isataeva et al. analyze the relationship between FDI, economic growth, the inflation rate, and the volume of international reserves in the context of Kazakhstan's economy. According to the scholars, international reserves have a significant positive influence on attracting FDI, while inflation did not exert a statistically significant impact within this model [7].

A. Kulanov et al. identified problems hindering the investment activity of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the Republic of Kazakhstan. According to the authors, a sufficiently favorable investment climate has formed in the Republic, and the authorities have done significant work to create conditions for business development. However, some problems in implementing SME investment projects persist. The most significant problems include underdeveloped transport and logistics infrastructure, a shortage of production and office space, as well as difficulties with land plot registration, attracting foreign labor, and obtaining various permits necessary for conducting business [8].

N. Demeuov et al. examined the features and components of the investment policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan by identifying its main directions and defining future development scenarios for industry as the primary economic sector [9].

Thus, many authors note that Kazakhstan's economy demonstrates stable growth and high investment potential, supported by active attraction of foreign investment and successful institutional reforms. Despite positive trends, problems related to infrastructure, bureaucracy, and risks persist, requiring further efforts to create a favorable investment climate and enhance the efficiency of industrial and small business development.

In order to attract investment, Kazakhstan is developing special economic zones, streamlining bureaucracy, improving infrastructure, supporting small businesses, promoting the country's image, and ensuring stable legislation.

A. Madaliyev writes that the government of Kazakhstan has taken measures to ensure stability and fulfill obligations to foreign investors: to reduce the excessive role of monopolies and oligopolies in the economy; and strives to increase the transparency of public procurement. However, approximately 50 percent of all national wealth is concentrated in the hands of 0.0001 percent of the population [10].

B. L. K. Kazbekov Chzhou believes that to attract potential investors to the Kazakhstani market, it is necessary, first and foremost, to reduce taxes and introduce stimulating incentives for investments in the manufacturing sector [11].

A. Ainur emphasizes the need to attract foreign investment by improving legal mechanisms and increasing transparency [12].

A. Panzabekova et al. developed proposals for improving the economic mechanisms for stimulating FDI in Kazakhstan's economy. A detailed description of the three-tier system for monitoring the investment climate in Kazakhstan is provided, and positive trends in improving the mechanisms for attracting FDI are identified. The scholars propose measures that would facilitate investors channeling funds into the manufacturing and innovation sectors of Kazakhstan's economy [13].

O. Baisalbek et al. point out that Kazakhstan faces the necessity of a large-scale transformation of the energy sector. The country requires significant investments in the development of renewable energy sources, hydrogen technologies, and the modernization of electrical infrastructure [14].

A number of scholars have developed specific proposals for investing in various sectors of Kazakhstan's economy, for example, in energy (renewable energy in Kazakhstan [15; 16], the "green" transition [17], opportunities for using green bonds [18], decarbonization [19], the energy transition [20], digitalization of energy infrastructure [21], etc.) and the modernization of oil and gas sector infrastructure [22; 23].

Attention is also paid to the modernization of agriculture, processing, and export of products. In particular, S. Gaisina notes that the current investment climate in Kazakhstan is not conducive to lending to the agricultural sector [24], while G. M. Zhurynov et al. state that the management of most agricultural enterprises does not recognize the importance of investment attractiveness and does not consciously

engage in issues of forming its assessment, developing methods for its analysis, testing them at the enterprise, or studying the factors influencing it [25].

The priority of developing the agro-industrial complex justifies the provision of state support to agricultural producers. The authors develop measures to ensure the accessibility of financial resources for agricultural producers [26].

Z. Kurbanov et al. investigate the link between perceived land rights and investments in movable agricultural property. The scholars emphasize significant investment incentives associated more with rights of use and management than with guarantees of ownership or transferability [27].

I. Feher and A. Fieldsend conclude that Kazakhstan possesses significant potential to expand wheat production and exports in the future and can play a substantial role in ensuring local, but particularly regional, food security. Investments in infrastructure and machinery will be crucial for unlocking the country's wheat potential and offsetting the potential impacts of climate change, water scarcity, and soil degradation [28].

Attention is also given by authors to the development of the IT sector, startups, and digital solutions (transformation towards Industry 4.0 [29], integration of artificial intelligence systems [30]), as well as the development of infrastructure and tourism projects [31].

Many researchers note the necessity of investing in the country's innovation economy, in particular [32; 33].

R. Sagyndykova et al. write about the need to transition to a new growth model and facilitate a significant expansion of the role of the non-resource-based, trade-oriented sector [34].

Scholars have assessed the innovative and investment activity of the West Kazakhstan region; identified opportunities for improving the operations of currently established special economic zones and creating new ones; and provided recommendations for their enhancement [35].

S. Beisembina et al. point to the importance of developing economic policy management strategies, including regulating tax rates, investment incentives, and other economic measures to ensure sustainable development [36].

There are proposals for the deep diversification of the country's economy, specifically creating a favorable overall environment, improving the education sector and workforce skills upgrading, as well as developing information infrastructure and the innovation sector [37].

Thus, for the sustainable development of Kazakhstan, it is necessary to implement a set of measures aimed at increasing transparency and legal protection for investors, reducing tax barriers, developing priority sectors (energy, agriculture, IT, innovation), modernizing infrastructure, and stimulating non-resource-based and innovative sectors. A crucial condition is the large-scale transformation of the energy and agricultural sectors, along with the creation of a favorable investment environment, which will attract long-term investments and ensure economic diversification.

RESULTS

FDI refers to investments where a foreign investor acquires a significant and long-term stake in a company of another country, typically involving ownership of 10% or more of the share capital. In addition to equity participation, FDI also accounts for debt instruments such as trade credits, loans, debt securities, and other liabilities, as well as reinvested earnings—that is, net profit minus distributed dividends.

According to UNCTAD data [38], the FDI inflow into Kazakhstan has been declining from 2022 to 2024 (see Table 1).

Table 1

FDI inflow in Central Asian countries (USD million)

Region/economy	2022	2023	2024	Growth rate (2022, 2023)	Growth rate (2023, 2024)
World	1,389,525.5	1,454,976.2	1,508,803.3	4.71%	3.70%
Central Asia	10,205.4	7,548.1	2,927.0	-26.04%	-61.22%
Kazakhstan	6,542.1	3,713.9	-2,550.5	-43.23%	-168.67%
Kyrgyzstan	54.9	159.0	705.3	189.62%	343.61%
Tajikistan	174.0	140.6	291.3	-19.22%	107.22%
Turkmenistan	936.0	1,378.3	1,644.8	47.25%	19.33%
Uzbekistan	2,498.3	2,156.4	2,836.1	-13.69%	31.52%

Source: www.unctad.org/fdistatistics

Thus, the growth rate of FDI inflow into Kazakhstan decreased by 43% from 2022 to 2023, and by 169% from 2023 to 2024.

The growth rate of investment outflow from Kazakhstan was -154% from 2022 to 2023, and decreased by 464% from 2023 to 2024 (see Table 2).

Table 2

FDI outflow from Central Asian countries (USD million)

Region/ economy	2022	2023	2024	Growth rate (2022, 2023)	Growth rate (2023, 2024)
World	1,568,612.9	1,556,106.5	1,608,873.9	-0.80%	3.39%
Central Asia	10,205.4	7,548.1	2,927.0	-26.04%	-61.22%
Kazakhstan	-1,831.1	989.6	-3,602.6	-154.05%	-464.04%
Kyrgyzstan	-1,392.5	929.8	-3,760.3	-166.77%	-504.41%
Tajikistan	-454.6	8.0	20.0	-101.76%	150.00%
Turkmenistan	12.0	40.0	101.0	234.08%	152.33%

Source: www.unctad.org/fdistatistics

The growth rate of FDI stocks in Kazakhstan increased by 2% from 2022 to 2023, and decreased by 4% from 2023 to 2024 (see Table 3).

Table 3

FDI stocks in Central Asian countries (USD million)

Region/ economy	2022	2023	2024	Growth rate (2022, 2023)	Growth rate (2023, 2024)
World	43,733,572.8	48,097,604.6	5,090,354.6	9.98%	5.84%
Central Asia	217,157.4	222,146.4	220,531.7	2.30%	-0.73%
Kazakhstan	154,940.4	157,562.2	151,307.1	1.69%	-3.97%
Kyrgyzstan	3,505.6	3,469.0	3,961.0	-1.04%	14.18%
Tajikistan	3,329.5	3,332.8	3,975.6	0.10%	19.29%
Turkmenistan	41,537.2	42,915.5	44,560.3	3.32%	3.83%
Uzbekistan	13,844.7	14,866.9	16,727.7	7.38%	12.52%

Source: www.unctad.org/fdistatistics

The volume of FDI in Kazakhstan increased by 3% from 2022 to 2023, and decreased by 14% from 2023 to 2024 (see Table 4).

Table 4

Volume of FDI in Central Asian countries (USD million)

Region/ economy	2022	2023	2024	Growth rate (2022, 2023)	Growth rate (2023, 2024)
World	39,492,628.8	42,596,580.9	43,594,995.4	7.86%	2.34%
Central Asia	17,456.6	17,999.5	15,884.0	3.11%	-11.75%

Kazakhstan	16,945.9	17,433.8	14,950.0	2.88%	-14.25%
Kyrgyzstan	25.9	33.0	48.0	27.41%	45.45%
Tajikistan	282.8	322.8	642.4	14.16%	99.01%
Uzbekistan	202.0	209.9	243.6	3.93%	16.06%

Source: www.unctad.org/fdistatistics

The value of announced FDI projects in Kazakhstan increased significantly from 2022 to 2023, but declined from 2023 to 2024 (see Tables 5 and 6).

Table 5

Value of announced greenfield FDI projects, by source,
in Central Asian countries (USD million)

Region/ economy	2022	2023	2024
Central Asia	34	1,132	295
Kazakhstan	34	258	136
Kyrgyzstan	-	127	-
Tajikistan	-	-	-
Turkmenistan	-	743	-
Uzbekistan	-	5	159

Source: www.unctad.org/fdistatistics

Table 6

Value of announced greenfield FDI projects, by destination,
in Central Asian countries (USD million)

Region/ economy	2022	2023	2024
Central Asia	11,444	31,818	27,178
Kazakhstan	1,640	18,468	17,953
Kyrgyzstan	33	1,173	2,851
Tajikistan	18	1,340	343
Turkmenistan	7,836	135	335
Uzbekistan	1,917	10,702	5,696

Source: www.fDimarkets.com

The number of announced greenfield FDI projects in Kazakhstan increased significantly from 2022 to 2023 and continued to grow from 2023 to 2024 (see Table 7).

Table 7

Number of announced greenfield FDI projects, by destination,
in Central Asian countries

Region/ economy	2022	2023	2024
Central Asia	49	158	187
Kazakhstan	28	65	81
Kyrgyzstan	1	8	15
Tajikistan	3	6	3
Turkmenistan	3	4	3
Uzbekistan	14	75	85

Source: www.fDimarkets.com

The National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan has published statistical data on FDI inflow for January–September 2025, which indicates stable growth and significant structural transformations in the economy's investment model. The National Bank compiles statistics on net FDI inflow or outflow using two methods: the assets and liabilities principle (or balance of payments) and the investment direction principle

Direct investment by direction of investment (position at the end of the period) shows the accumulated volume of investments directed abroad and received by Kazakhstan from abroad as of a specific date (see Table 8).

Table 8

Direct investment by direction of investment:
position at the end of the period (USD million)

	As of 01.01.2022	As of 01.01.2023	As of 01.01.2024	As of 01.10.2025
Direct investment abroad	152,664.2	159,074.3	155,568.7	151,209.8
Direct investment into Kazakhstan	72,866.9	81,359.3	81,488.0	75,652.5

The dynamics from 2022 to 2025 show a declining trend in direct investment into Kazakhstan. Despite the decrease, the mining industry, trade, and manufacturing remain the dominant sectors, with investors from Russia, the Netherlands, South Korea, Belgium, and China leading the way.

The gross inflow of FDI into Kazakhstan decreased notably in 2024, falling by approximately 28% compared to 2023 (see Table 4). This resulted in the first recorded

net outflow of FDI, primarily due to reduced investments in the mining sector (oil and gas sphere). However, 2025 witnessed growth in certain sectors (e.g., financial and insurance activities), and the overall situation is viewed as a temporary phenomenon, with hopes for recovery driven by new projects. Meanwhile, domestic investments and budgetary expenditures helped partially offset the decline.

Table 9

Gross inflow of direct investment into Kazakhstan from foreign direct investors
by type of resident economic activity

Name of Activity	2022	2023	2024	2025
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	32.5	49.5	26.5	41.2
Mining and quarrying	12,080.0	8,626.8	6,371.4	2,656.6
Manufacturing	5,554.2	5,378.7	2,951.4	3,180.7
Information and communication	394.7	378.5	571.9	1,309.4
Financial and insurance activities	650.6	939.9	529.9	2,512.5
Real estate operations	102.7	379.3	-6.4	123.4
Professional, scientific and technical activities	1,250.7	368.8	905.3	118.0
Administrative and support service activities	130.8	85.9	74.4	1.7
Public administration and defense; compulsory social security				
Education, healthcare and social services; arts, entertainment and recreation	60.5	38.1	32.1	73.4
Provision of other services	35.4	30.0	98.8	157.2
Total	28,171	23,866	17,761	14,895

Source: [39]

The decline in gross FDI inflow has cast doubt on the attainability of the target indicators established within the Investment Policy Concept of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2029. It has also created uncertainty in the authorities' understanding of the actual state of the country's investment climate. According to the plans of the Ministry of National Economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the volume of gross FDI inflow was supposed to reach USD 24.8 billion by the end of 2024. However, expectations were not met: the actual volume of foreign investment turned out to be 30.8% below the planned target.

DISCUSSION

Thus, in 2024, Kazakhstan experienced a decrease in the volume of FDI. A negative net investment flow was recorded for the first time – amounting to 2.6 billion dollars, indicating a capital outflow from the country. The main decline occurred in the oil and gas sector and the financial sphere, whereas growth was observed in trade and information technology. According to analysts, the decline in the oil and gas industry is associated with the completion of major projects and a potential decrease in investor demand for new initiatives due to oil price volatility [40]. Overall, the current indicators highlight the need to revise the model for attracting investment to Kazakhstan – with an emphasis on developing the private sector and non-resource-based, high-tech industries. It is also necessary to acknowledge the need for developing democratic institutions that protect foreign investors [41], implementing public-private partnership programs [42], and fostering friendly international relations [43].

Net FDI inflow differs from gross inflow in that its structure does not account for depreciation expenses on existing projects with foreign investor participation. In other words, net inflow represents “new” funds entering the country, while the gross indicator includes all investments, including those already invested and “operating” assets. The situation with net FDI inflow is a cause for serious concern. For the first time in recent years, this indicator turned negative, indicating that money is being withdrawn from the country rather than new investments entering. In 2023, foreign investors reinvested 6.8 billion dollars into Kazakhstani projects, channeling their earned profits back into development, whereas in 2024 they chose to withdraw these funds from the Kazakh economy.

According to representatives of state bodies, it is necessary to strengthen the protection of investor rights, which involves improving the “prosecutorial filter” mechanism to ensure transparency in decision-making by government agencies [44].

The simultaneous decrease in both the inflow and outflow of FDI may indicate stabilization or a reduction in the overall investment flow into the country. In particular, the decline in inflow reflects a decrease in the volume of new investments, often caused by a reduction in the country’s investment attractiveness or the impact of external factors, such as global macroeconomic conditions. At the same time, the reduction in outflow points to decreased investor activity in withdrawing capital, which may indicate growing uncertainty or a lack of sustainable investment growth. Such a combination of changes points to a trend of stagnation in the inflow of

foreign investment and a decrease in the withdrawal of existing capital, which, in turn, may signal the need for measures to improve the investment climate or revise strategies for attracting capital into the economy.

CONCLUSION

Despite the continued reliance on hydrocarbon and mineral resources as key pillars of the economy, the government of Kazakhstan is undertaking measures to diversify the economic structure. Active engagement with foreign investors is carried out through official institutions, such as the Foreign Investors Council under the President, as well as through bilateral negotiation formats. Geopolitical events, such as the conflict in Russia against Ukraine and the associated sanctions, have impacted Kazakhstan's economic stability. Given the extensive shared border and significant economic ties with Russia, compliance with Western sanctions regimes has caused certain economic disruptions. Nonetheless, the country's macroeconomic resilience is largely supported by favorable conditions in commodity markets and high prices for exported resources. The program of economic reforms initiated by President Kassym-Jomart Tokayev is focused on diversifying the economy, stimulating the development of the industrial sector, expanding privatization, and seeking alternative trade routes. Large-scale tax reforms are anticipated in 2026. However, regulatory volatility, localization and import substitution policies, and persistent corruption remain concerns for foreign investors. They point to the need for strengthening the rule of law, more predictable and transparent tax and regulatory systems, investment in human capital, development of modern transport and logistics infrastructure, as well as more favorable conditions for obtaining work permits.

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The author have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Daniela Antonescu. Romanian Academy (Romania)